

RESEARCH PAPER

Title :- Effect of Federal Subsidies on Crop Fields in Tamil Nadu

Research Question :- To what extent have the subsidies belonging to the agricultural group of subsidies, affected the growth of paddy crop, in the Western District of Pudukkottai in Tamil Nadu?

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Introduction :

The Primary sector, which can be called the Agricultural sector, leads to economic growth and economic development. By economic growth and development, poverty will be eradicated in a country like India. The main crop in India is rice, and the largest producer of rice is the state of Tamil Nadu. The primary sector contributes mainly to the country's GDP, where the majority of the people are living in the rural areas, and are employed in this sector. The area of focus for my research is Pudukkottai, and it is one of the districts of TamilNadu where a high concentration of farmers, with small land holdings constitute the industry. These farmers face several setbacks, lack of resources, limited access to budget expenditure, and have no access to any sort of irrigation methods. To meet the challenges of the farmers, many Subsidy Schemes have been introduced and implemented in India, with the intention of giving support to the smaller farmers, in order to increase their efficiency in agriculture.

Subsidies are a set of budgets set and used by the government, to increase the economic growth and provide financial support to specified sections of the economy. In the primary sector, where subsidies are provided to buy inputs like seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides, to develop the field of irrigation, infrastructure and technology. Despite the intention of subsidies, their effectiveness and impact are still widely debated upon. One way to increase the level of efficiency, is agricultural growth that can lead to overproduction depending on the government, through subsidy, due to the severity of these subsidies, it is highly questionable whether primary sectors would be sustainable in the area of depletion of natural resources, environmental degradation, and change in the climatic conditions.

This essay seeks to explore the effect of subsidies on rice farms in Pudukkottai. This essay describes the consequences of the schemes implemented by the government of India, in the field of agricultural efficiency, income of the agriculturalist, and lifting up the agricultural community, in Pudukkottai.

This analysis will be conducted by an elaborate study on the topic, secondary data which is factually backed and cited. This analysis will be conducted by thorough study on the topic, secondary research data that is factually backed and cited The essay will also evaluate the effectiveness of subsidy programs in promoting sustainable and equitable agricultural growth and identify potential ways to improve the current system to better support smallholder farmers in Pudukkottai.

Through the use of a variety of Infrastructure Facilities namely, State Seed Farm (SSF) - Annapannai, Pulses Seed Multiplication Farm (PSMF) - Vamban, SOSF - Vellala Viduthi, the Extended Essay discusses the short run production costs to the firm, long run production costs to the firm, effects of the subsidy on the firm, effects to the economy's subsidy rate in the long run and short run, calculating the effectiveness of the subsidy and discusses potential changes to the utilization of subsidies to allow firms to achieve profit maximization. The significance of this study lies in the fact that smallholder farmers in Pudukkottai face several challenges that limit their productivity and income.

These challenges include poor access to credit, lack of irrigation infrastructure, and poor access to markets. The effectiveness of subsidies in addressing these challenges and promoting agricultural growth is, therefore, crucial. The study will also contribute to the role of subsidies in promoting agricultural growth and development.

In the first section of the essay, a review on subsidy is done, based on its effectiveness, and the consequences of the subsidy schemes for small farmers. The second section will provide a brief overview of the rice farming industry in Pudukkottai, and the specific subsidy programs implemented in the region. The third section will present the results of the secondary research, and the involved critical analysis, and the fourth section will analyze and provide an evaluation of the effectiveness of subsidies in promoting sustainable and equitable agricultural growth in Pudukkottai.

Methodology :

The research methodology used for this study includes methods to understand the impact of subsidies on rice farms in Pudukkottai. The study started with a review of the published documents from the Tamil Nadu state government's website. Subsequently, data was collected from other secondary sources in the chosen farms' from the Pudukkottai District's Agriculture website, and other online agricultural journals, publishing studies across the Districts in Tamil Nadu.

A set of 3 farms were chosen for the survey. The three largest producers of rice in terms of revenue, per capita crop yield, and profitability. The study focused on rice farmers in the Western District of Pudukkottai, Tamil Nadu, and the sample size was 3 farms. The essay evaluates the subsidies used by the farm, other economic decisions that act as an integral part of the effectiveness of the subsidy, and the amount of profit yielded, as a result of implementing the subsidy.

The secondary data used was the annual budgeting, budgeting history, and allocated monetary resource sheets from the economics departments at all 3 of the aforementioned farms. The secondary data was collected from various sources, including the state website, farm reports, and district diagnostic studies. The secondary data collected, was analyzed using the evaluation techniques, such as the effectiveness of economic integration, maximum usage of subsidiary data collected, and was analyzed to identify patterns that emerged from the secondary data.

These data were used only for research purposes. The study also adhered to the principles of intellectual property and plagiarism and all the sources used in the study were appropriately cited and referenced. Overall, the various methods used in this study, allowed for a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of subsidies on rice farms in Pudukkottai. The use of both quantitative and qualitative research methods enabled me to compile the data and validate the resulting findings, and measure the potential gain due to the implementation of subsidies.

Theoretical Hypothesis :

A subsidy is a kind of financial help for the firms given by the government, designed to promote an economic objective. In the context of agriculture, subsidies are commonly used to support farmers by providing financial assistance for inputs like seeds, fertilizers and pesticides, irrigation budgets, machineries and technology, by the responsible governmental bodies.

Subsidies can be of different types, including direct payments, tax breaks, and loan guarantees. While subsidies can provide important support to certain industries or groups, they can also have unintended consequences. They can create market distortions, reduce incentives for innovation, and contribute to environmental degradation or social inequality. As a result, governments need to be cautious and careful while implementing specific subsidies, and ensure they achieve their environmental objectives in an ecologically sustainable manner.

Subsidies can make a significant impact on agriculture by providing financial support to farmers and promoting sustainable agriculture practices. Subsidies can also encourage farmers to adopt sustainable agriculture practices by providing financial incentives for activities like organic farming, integrated pest management, and conservation agriculture. This can help improve soil health, and promote biodiversity. Subsidies can help farmers in Pudukkottai access inputs like seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides at lower prices, which can improve crop yields and reduce costs.

This is important for small farmers who may have limited access to credit and other resources. Subsidies for irrigation can help farmers in Pudukkottai, access water for irrigation, which is important for crop growth in areas with a lower amount of rainfall (during the summer season in specific). Subsidies for farm mechanization can help farmers adopt modern farm machinery, which can reduce drudgery and improve the efficiency of farming operations. This can help farmers save time and labor, and increase their productivity and income. Subsidies for credit can help farmers access finance for agricultural activities at lower interest rates. This can improve farmers' access to finance and reduce their dependence on informal sources of credit, which can be expensive and risky. The governments of these states have implemented various schemes and programs aimed at supporting farmers and promoting sustainable agriculture practices.

Some of the main subsidies and programs that have been implemented in South India include those related to irrigation, mechanization, organic farming, and crop insurance. These subsidies and programs have helped farmers improve their yields, reduce costs, and increase their income.

The central government's PMKSY Subsidy Scheme, Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) and Soil Health Card (SHC) schemes have had a significant impact on farmers in South India. These schemes provide financial assistance and support for crop insurance and soil health management, respectively. The trend of subsidies for crop growth in South India has been a positive growth in recent years, and the government continues to introduce new programs and schemes aimed at supporting farmers and promoting sustainable agriculture practices.

Figure 1 : A graph depicting the changes occurring due to subsidies.

In the graph shown above, the Y-Axis represents the price, and the X-axis represents the quantity demanded. The equilibrium point is drawn where the supply and demand curves intersect, and represents the market price and quantity of the product or service in the absence of a subsidy.

When a subsidy is introduced, the cost of production will be reduced inadvertently, increasing the supply. As a result, the market price decreases and the quantity demanded increases. The new equilibrium point occurs at a lower price (p_1) and a higher quantity (q_1). The height of the subsidy is represented by the vertical distance between the two supply curves.

Agriculture Subsidies Available to Farmers in the Western District of Pudukkottai, in Tamil Nadu :

1. National Food Security Mission (NFSM)
2. Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY)
3. Paramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojana (PKVY)
4. Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY)
5. Kisan Credit Card (KCC)
6. Soil Health Card (SHC) Scheme

How do subsidies impact crop growth in south indian farms?

Subsidies can have a significant impact on crop growth in South Indian farms. Subsidies are grants provided by the government to farmers in Pudukkottai, to encourage the adoption of modern technologies, such as fertigation units, combine harvester, improved irrigation systems, and other modern machinery. These technologies can help with the rise in the level of productivity, improve crop quality, and reduce production costs, which leads to higher profits for farmers. One of the major impacts of subsidies on crop growth in South Indian farms is the adoption of high-yielding crop varieties, which can significantly increase crop yields. Normally, subsidies are provided to get a higher yield from hybrid rice varieties, in comparison to the traditional varieties. This has led to the tremendous improvement in the income of the farmers in the District of Pudukkottai. At the same time, subsidies will reduce the cost of production, and stimulate the farmers of Pudukkottai, to invest in rather modern methods of irrigation, to increase the crop yield.

Subsidies also allow farmers to invest in modern irrigation systems, this improves the systems built for water management, and increase crop yields drastically. In regions with water scarcity, subsidies for drip irrigation and other efficient irrigation systems can be particularly beneficial. Moreover, subsidies increase the use of large machineries such as tractors and harvesters, which can significantly reduce labor costs and increase efficiency in farming operations. Subsidies for machinery can also lead to timely and efficient farm operations, which can help ensure timely planting and harvesting and can lead to improved crop yields. All in all, subsidies can have a very positive impact on crop growth in South Indian farms by promoting the adoption of modern technologies.

Latest technology will improve the level of efficiency, showing the quality of the crops in an improved manner, thereby reducing the cost of production, where the profits will be maximized for the farmers of the District of Pudukkottai

Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana (PMKSY) Subsidy Scheme:

The Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchayee Yojana (PMKSY)¹ is a subsidy program initiated by the Government of India in 2015 to promote the development of irrigation-based farming in India. The program aims to provide a permanent solution to the irrigation requirements of farmers by focusing on the development of efficient water management systems and infrastructure.

Under the PMKSY, farmers in Pudukkottai can avail financial assistance for the creation of irrigation infrastructure, such as bore wells, dug wells, tube wells, lift irrigation, and micro-irrigation systems. The subsidy is about 90% of the cost for small farmers and up to 80% of the cost for other farmers with access to most far resources. The remaining cost is borne by the farmer as their share.

The PMKSY program has three components, namely:

Accelerated Irrigation Benefits Program - The AIBP component focuses on the completion of irrigation projects that have been pending for a long time.

Har Khet Ko Pani - This component is aimed at providing end-to-end solutions to create new water sources, distribution networks and farm-level applications to achieve the goal of "Har Khet Ko Pani" (water to every farm).

Per Drop More Crop - The PDMC component is aimed at promoting efficient water management practices such as micro-irrigation, reuse of treated wastewater, precision irrigation, and other technologies to achieve "more crop per drop."

The PMKSY subsidy is available to all farmers, including small and marginal farmers, and is implemented by the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD). To meet the challenges like shortage of water, changes in climatic conditions, level of efficiency, and the level of economic well being, where subsidies play a vital role. One of the subsidy schemes namely, Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchayee Yojana, will stimulate the progress and management of the irrigation infrastructure, and make sure there is sustainability in the primary sector.

¹"Pmksy Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchayee Yojana." *Press Information Bureau*, TNAU, 12 Apr. 2018, pib.gov.in/PressReleaselframePage.aspx?PRID=1848470.

Effect on the survivability of Potable Groundwater due to Agriculture Subsidies :

If agricultural farmers are provided with subsidies, the potable groundwater will face a large impact, by making more use of water resources. Agricultural farmers will be stimulated to use more water resources because the cost is being reduced. Though a large impact will take place, the specific use of groundwater will be more that will lead to depletion of aquifers and this in turn, will reduce the level of groundwater. Due to the above impact, many regions where people rely on potable water will have less access towards it. Normally, agricultural subsidies will encourage rural people to preserve the water resources and groundwater quality. For example drip irrigation, rainwater harvesting and water saving techniques will certainly reduce the usage of water and improve the quality and quantity of groundwater resources. The consequences of agricultural subsidies mainly depend on the policies and practices followed in the region.

Low Agricultural Electricity Prices due to Subsidies:

Low agricultural electricity prices can have several effects on the agricultural sector. Cost of farming operations has a chance to be lowered, as a benefit derived from the lowering of electricity prices. Electricity is a major contributor for many agricultural activities. This includes irrigation, mechanization, and storage, among others. Lower electricity prices can help farmers reduce their costs of production, and their economies of scale, which essentially means lower prices for consumers and increased competition in, and between farmers.

However, low agricultural electricity prices can also have some negative effects on the sector. If there is a fall in electricity prices, there is a chance of misusing the water resources. At the same time, farmers will not be in a position to carry out the latest technologies, like drip irrigation, or rainwater harvesting. Another potential negative effect of low agricultural electricity prices is that it can discourage investment in renewable energy technologies.

Finally, low agricultural electricity prices can also have implications for government finances. When electricity prices are low, it makes no sense for the government to provide subsidies which may not cover their costs to run the industry. For most of the developing countries, the government budget will be at a deficit, where there will be a lack of funds. Lower agricultural electricity prices can have both positive and negative effects on the agricultural sector. While lower prices could possibly reduce the cost of farming operations, they also increase competitiveness, and can also lead to the overuse of resources. As such, it is important to

carefully consider the implications of electricity pricing policies on the agricultural sector and broader economic and environmental goals.

Analysis and Evaluation of Secondary Data :

In a Ground Water Summary report² released by the Agricultural Department in Pudukkottai, in the Financial Year 2014 before the PMKSY Subsidy Scheme's implementation, the Dynamic Groundwater Resources Estimation of Farms in Pudukkottai, were as follows. **SOSF, Vellalaviduthy in Karambakudi** had a Net Annual Groundwater Availability of 2190.65 hectare meters. The Existing Gross Ground Water Draft, set for irrigation, of 517.80 hectare meters. The Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for Domestic and Individual Water Supply, was 42.62 hectare meters, and finally the Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for all Uses, was 560.42 hectare meters, which placed the farm's revenue firka at the "SAFE" status, meaning the farm is not exposed to monetary punitive damages, even in the case of a reduction in subsidy.

Moving forward with the Second Farm, **Pulses Seed Multiplication Farm (PSMF), Vamban in Alangudi**, had a Net Annual Groundwater Availability of 2670.63 hectare meters. The Existing Gross Ground Water Draft, set for irrigation, of 1962.8 hectare meters. The Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for Domestic and Individual Water Supply, was 64 hectare meters, and finally the Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for all Uses, was 2026.80 hectare meters, which placed the farm's revenue firka at the "SEMI-CRITICAL" status, meaning the farm is exposed to monetary punitive damages, in the case of a reduction of subsidy.

Finally, moving on with the **State Seed Farm (SSF), Annapannai in Kudumiyanmalai**, had a Net Annual Groundwater Availability of 1978.53 hectare meters. The Existing Gross Ground Water Draft, set for irrigation, of 897.93 hectare meters. The Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for Domestic and Individual Water Supply, was 53.84 hectare meters, and finally the Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for all Uses, was 951.76 hectare meters, which placed the farm's revenue firka at the "SAFE" status, meaning the farm is not exposed to monetary punitive damages, even in the case of a reduction of subsidy by the government.

² "National Water Mission, Ministry of Jal Shakti, Department of Water." *GROUND WATER RESOURCES PUDUKOTTAI DISTRICT*, The State Ground and Surface Water Resources Data Centre, 22 May 2022, nwm.gov.in/sites/default/files/A%20note%20on%20State%20Water%20Budgeting%2019.3.2018.pdf.

This, however, was with a subsidy budget of 72.75 crore INR, shown by the Fund Allocation letter,³ sent to “The Mission Directors of All States/Implementing Agencies” by the serving Commissioner of the Horticulture Division, in the Department of Agriculture and Cooperation, Government of India. With the PMKSY Subsidy Scheme setting a budget of 50,000 crores INR for the 5-year long duration of the subsidy,

Since the introduction of the PMKSY Subsidy Scheme, the scheme’s Har Khet Ko Pani⁴ initiative, has allowed farmers in the 3 aforementioned farms in specific, to achieve their farms’ respective goals, by helping the farmers with financial assistance, in purchasing the necessary technologies required, to achieve their annual productivity target. The scheme’s objectives are to assuredly provide the farms with proper, and functional irrigation sources, facilitate physical access onto the farm to expand the cultivable area, improvise the efficiency of water use, achieve the reduction of migrating farmers from agricultural to non-agricultural sectors. Then, the subsidy scheme focuses on eliminating the amount of barren land, and finally increasing productivity and production capabilities. This is all, such that after the 5-year term is over, the small farmers communities are uplifted and they are living under good habitable conditions, and their respective farms are under a good “economic status”. In the 3 farms mentioned above, and Pudukkottai in general, 60% of the subsidy fundings are from the Union Government, and 40% are from the State Government.

³ Prakash, Om. “22052015.” *Fund Allocation for FY 2015-2016 - Annexure*, Department of Agriculture and Cooperation (Horticulture Division), 14 July 2018, pmksy.gov.in/microirrigation/Archive/22052015.pdf.

⁴ India, Government of. “Micro Irrigation Fund - Pmksy.gov.in.” *Har Khet Ko Pani - Introduction - Groundwater Irrigation*, Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchayee Yojana, 14 Sept. 2015, pmksy.gov.in/MicroIrrigation/Archive/Guideline_MIF03082018.pdf.

After the implementation of this Subsidy Scheme in Pudukkottai, environmental state departments across India, started noting the amount of impact this subsidy was making on the nation. On the 4th February 2022, the Ministry of Food Processing Industries (MoFPI), Government of India has announced the Continuation of the central sector umbrella scheme PMKSY for the period until the Fiscal Year 2025-26.

A report announced by the Head of the Ministry of Jal Shakti, Shri Bisheshwar Tudu, on August the 4th 2022, in a written reply in the Lok Sabha, states that there have been numerous agricultural achievements due to the implementation of various PMKSY Subsidy Scheme Initiatives, between the financial years 2016 and 2022. A few notable examples are, The Accelerated Benefit Programme has increased the irrigation potential by 24.35 lakh hectares. The Command Area Development and Water Management Programme, covered a net total cultivable land of almost 16.42 lakh hectares. The Har Khet Ko Pani Programme surfaced minor irrigation potential, and has created 2.58 lakh hectares of new irrigable land. The same initiative has created a cultivable groundwater base of about 2.58 lakh hectares. The Per Crop More Drop Programme, has covered 61.72 lakh hectares under Micro-Irrigation, and finally the Watershed Development initiative has covered over 14.54 lakh hectares of irrigable land, and brought it under protective irrigation.

All these ecological, environmental, and agricultural achievements have been achieved as a result of the implementation of the PMKSY Subsidy scheme, and under the impression that the “*Ceteris Paribus*”⁵ economic and agricultural conditions prevail, the projected growth for this subsidy in the future is also exponentially high.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, the Agricultural group of subsidies has had a significant impact on the growth of paddy crops in the Western District of Pudukkottai in Tamil Nadu. The subsidies have led to an increase in the use of Agricultural rice seeds, which have been shown to increase yields and income for farmers. In addition, the subsidies have also encouraged farmers to adopt newer practices today, such as drip irrigation and better soil management systems, which have definitely increased the crop yields by a large margin.

However, the effectiveness of the subsidies has been limited by certain challenges that I faced during the process of data collection, like lack of awareness and knowledge about the subsidies

⁵ Liberto, Daniel, and Toby Walters. *What Does Ceteris Paribus Mean in Economics?*, Investopedia, 27 Nov. 2007, www.investopedia.com/terms/c/ceterisparibus.asp.

for all the farmers, and the difficulties in informing them about subsidies. In most developing countries like India, there is a delay in providing the subsidies or the inability to provide subsidies, due to the political influence. These situations served as speed breakers in my essay, but enhanced the amount of data I could receive in the end. Despite any of these challenges, the method used could have benefited from an increased availability of resources. Despite these challenges, it is clear that the Agricultural group of subsidies has played a critical role in enhancing the growth of paddy crops in the Western District of Pudukkottai, and that is what this essay has strived to achieve.

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APPENDIX :

Dynamic Ground Water Resources Estimation of TamilNadu As on March 2013

District Summary

(in ha.m)

PUDUKOTTAI DISTRICT							
SI.No (District))	District	Net Annual Ground Water Availability	Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for Irrigation	Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for domestic and industrial water supply	Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for All uses (4+5)	Stage of Ground Water Development $\{(6/3)*100\}$ %	No of Over Exploited Firkas
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	PUDUKOTTAI	98,591.79	36,092.10	2,184.25	38,276.35	39	7

Firka Wise Summary

(in ha.m)

PUDUKOTTAI DISTRICT							
SI.No	Assessment Unit (Firka)	Net Annual Ground Water Availability	Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for Irrigation	Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for domestic and industrial	Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for All uses (4+5)	Stage of Ground Water Development $\{(6/3)*100\}$ %	Category of the Firka

				water supply			
1	ALANGUDI	2,670.63	1,962.80	64.00	2,026.80	76	SEMI CRITICAL
2	ARANTHANGI	2,306.68	308.00	41.13	349.13	15	SAFE
3	ARASAMALAI	1,680.80	905.00	33.88	938.88	56	SAFE
4	ARASARKULAM	1,726.83	1,324.65	43.10	1,367.75	79	SEMI CRITICAL
5	ATHANI	1,078.84	84.00	342.42	426.42	40	SAFE
6	AVUDAIYARKOIL	3,470.13	22.00	33.54	55.54	2	SAFE
7	EMBAL	3,187.85	240.75	22.08	262.83	8	SAFE

PUDUKOTTAI DISTRICT							
Sl.No	Assessment Unit (Firka)	Net Annual Ground Water Availability	Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for Irrigation	Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for domestic and industrial water supply	Existing Gross Ground Water Draft for All uses (4+5)	Stage of Ground Water Development $\{(6/3)*100\}$ %	Category of the Firka
8	GANDARVAKOTTAI	2,190.65	517.80	42.62	560.42	26	SAFE
9	ILLUPPUR	2,474.52	816.20	49.17	865.37	35	SAFE
10	KALLAKKOTTAI	2,219.94	1,249.80	40.97	1,290.77	58	SAFE
11	KARAIYUR	1,675.14	1,140.73	49.18	1,189.91	71	SEMI CRITICAL
12	KARAMBAKUDI	2,576.55	1,009.45	61.68	1,071.13	42	SAFE
13	KEELANILAI	3,122.12	645.60	36.32	681.92	22	SAFE
14	KEERAMANGALAM	2,043.06	1,685.20	54.80	1,740.00	85	SEMI CRITICAL
15	KEERANUR	2,049.94	1,010.75	33.97	1,044.72	51	SAFE
16	KILLUKKOTTAI	2,513.44	610.00	33.39	643.39	26	SAFE
17	KODUMBALUR	2,004.08	1,096.40	48.07	1,144.47	57	SAFE
18	KOTTAIPATTINAM	-	-	-	-	--	SALINE
19	KOTTUR	1,112.68	305.80	31.92	337.72	30	SAFE

20	KUDUMIYANMALAI	1,978.53	897.93	53.84	951.76	48	SAFE
21	KUNNANDARKOIL	2,957.17	727.30	51.40	778.70	26	SAFE
22	MALAIYUR	5,765.18	3,429.30	75.85	3,505.15	61	SAFE
23	MANAMELKUDI	3,107.49	186.60	62.93	249.53	8	SAFE
24	MIMISAL	4,040.79	3.00	61.17	64.17	2	SAFE
25	NAGUDI	1,659.27	220.00	36.38	256.38	15	SAFE
26	NARTHAMALAI	1,100.00	705.90	40.59	746.49	68	SAFE
27	NEERPALANI	2,854.08	1,711.45	54.22	1,765.67	62	SAFE
28	PERUMARUTHUR	-	-	-	-	--	SALINE
29	PONNAMARAVATHY	1,650.94	1,016.80	45.75	1,062.55	64	SAFE
30	PONPETTE	3,633.12	-	36.64	36.64	1	SAFE
31	POOVATHAKUDI	2,839.85	625.80	51.24	677.04	24	SAFE
32	PUDUKKOTTAI	1,589.27	622.75	56.21	678.96	43	SAFE
33	PUDUNAGAR	2,793.13	1,823.50	28.07	1,851.57	66	SAFE
34	SENGEERAI	2,873.79	912.40	33.97	946.37	33	SAFE
35	SILATTUR	2,637.76	350.00	85.36	435.36	17	SAFE
36	SINKAVANAM	-	-	-	-	--	SALINE
37	SITHANAVASAL	1,567.74	489.20	20.32	509.52	33	SAFE
38	THIRUMAYAM	2,142.99	149.70	51.58	201.28	9	SAFE
39	VALLANADU	2,010.85	1,220.25	32.87	1,253.12	62	SAFE
40	VARAPPUR	3,140.57	1,951.85	52.06	2,003.91	64	SAFE
41	VEERAPATTY	1,850.17	1,042.30	26.79	1,069.09	58	SAFE
42	VENNAVALKUDI	2,368.13	1,174.70	37.40	1,212.10	51	SAFE

38	THIRUMAYAM	2,142.99	149.70	51.58	201.28	9	SAFE
39	VALLANADU	2,010.85	1,220.25	32.87	1,253.12	62	SAFE
40	VARAPPUR	3,140.57	1,951.85	52.06	2,003.91	64	SAFE
41	VEERAPATTY	1,850.17	1,042.30	26.79	1,069.09	58	SAFE
42	VENNAVALKUDI	2,368.13	1,174.70	37.40	1,212.10	51	SAFE
43	VIRACHILAI	1,444.14	20.00	30.43	50.43	3	SAFE
44	VIRALIMALAI	2,482.97	1,876.45	96.98	1,973.43	79	SEMI CRITICAL
TOTAL		98,591.79	36,092.10	2,184.25	38,276.35	39	

Annexure

Fund Allocation for 2015-16 under Micro Irrigation Scheme

Rs in Crore

S.No.	State	Allocation
1	Andhra Pradesh	131.75
2	Bihar	20.00
3	Chattisgarh	7.50
4	Goa	0.15
5	Gujarat	146.75
6	Haryana	34.50
7	Himachal Pradesh	1.50
8	Jharkhand	15.00
9	Jammu & Kashmir	5.00
10	Karnataka	111.75
11	Kerala	5.00
12	Madhya Pradesh	82.75
13	Maharashtra	176.75
14	Odisha	12.00
15	Punjab	10.00
16	Rajasthan	104.75
17	Tamil Nadu	72.75
18	Telangana	92.75
19	Uttrakhand	7.00
20	Uttar Pradesh	15.00
21	West Bengal	5.00
NE States		
22	Arunachal Pradesh	0.50
23	Assam	1.00
24	Manipur	2.72
25	Meghalaya	0.50
26	Mizoram	4.50
27	Nagaland	0.00
28	Sikkim	4.26
29	Tripura	2.00
30	NCPAH	2.30
	Total	1075.43